

Multi-Objective Evolutionary Pathfinding in Path-Influenced Environments

Supplementary Materials

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1 Supplementary Materials

This file contains additional results of our study on multi-objective evolutionary pathfinding in path-influenced environments. Table 1 and Figure 4 show the detailed results of the C-metric evaluations. The Hypervolume diagrams for all shifting strategies on each map can be found in Figure 1. Moreover, we show the results of our GD^+ calculations in Figure 2 and of IGD^+ in Figure 3. The paths found by NSGA-II on all of our problem instances can be seen in Figure 5 and the Pareto fronts of all algorithms on each problem instance in Figure 6.

Table 1: Dominated Solutions of the Pareto optimal solutions found by the other algorithms in % to determine convergence performance of algorithms per problem instance (Worst and best converging results per scenario highlighted)

Shifting Strategy	Algorithm	Linear Gradient Map	Radial Gradient Map	Sinusoidal Map	River Map
LR Shift	NSGA-II	52.15	55.26	36.91	45.37
	NSGA-III	16.08	12.59	36.91	23.83
	SPEA-II	58.80	61.84	45.24	64.85
	RNSGA-II	43.31	49.83	56.35	49.99
	AGEMOEA	76.27	59.92	49.21	71.81
	DNSGA2	23.90	18.57	15.08	10.06
	SMSEMOA	54.92	49.26	22.62	47.75
MR Shift	NSGA-II	x	53.55	53.12	56.83
	NSGA-III	x	17.64	29.15	20.68
	SPEA-II	x	44.35	71.89	81.56
	RNSGA-II	x	43.63	39.88	32.75
	AGEMOEA	x	55.97	40.29	65.65
	DNSGA2	x	19.33	14.71	6.86
	SMSEMOA	x	43.39	35.50	34.87
S2 Shift	NSGA-II	18.63	57.43	51.40	44.42
	NSGA-III	31.67	18.65	12.12	8.57
	SPEA-II	53.77	52.30	56.13	72.68
	RNSGA-II	45.07	60.43	70.80	63.87
	AGEMOEA	56.96	54.30	49.76	71.43
	DNSGA2	2.01	15.31	3.03	7.74
	SMSEMOA	35.96	64.32	48.99	39.29
S3 Shift	NSGA-II	x	13.33	x	72.71
	NSGA-III	x	2.22	x	21.19
	SPEA-II	x	8.88	x	55.51
	RNSGA-II	x	13.33	x	62.72
	AGEMOEA	x	13.33	x	39.44
	DNSGA2	x	9.99	x	4.46
	SMSEMOA	x	13.33	x	16.33
EN Shift	NSGA-II	100.00	25.12	58.89	55.58
	NSGA-III	33.33	10.96	60.56	32.72
	SPEA-II	100.00	11.07	43.06	46.96
	RNSGA-II	16.67	20.27	58.89	45.63
	AGEMOEA	66.67	23.67	21.39	78.98
	DNSGA2	66.67	9.31	7.50	20.93
	SMSEMOA	0.00	17.59	60.83	53.69

Fig. 1: Average Hypervolume and Standard deviation over all seeds for all algorithms on each Map using each Shifting Strategy

Fig. 2: Average GD^+ and Standard deviation over all seeds for all algorithms on each Map using each Shifting Strategy

Fig. 3: Average IGD^+ and Standard deviation over all seeds for all algorithms on each Map using each Shifting Strategy

Fig 4: C-Metric comparison between algorithms per map and per shifting strategy

Fig. 5: Paths found by algorithms per map and per shifting strategy

Fig. 6: Pareto Fronts per Map and per Shifting Strategy